

Environmental approach of an enhanced geothermal system for energy efficient building retrofitting in a decentralized context

Ewa Alicja Zukowska¹, Maria Parascanu¹, Henrikki Pieskä², Jose Jorge Espi Gallart¹, Frederic Clarens Blanco¹, Marco Calderoni³, Qian Wang^{2,4}

¹ Eurecat, Centre Tecnològic de Catalunya, Waste, Energy and Environmental Impact Unit. Manresa, Spain

² Department of Civil and Architectural Engineering, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Brinellvägen 23, Stockholm, Sweden

³ R2M Solution s.r.l., Polo Tecnologico di Pavia, Via Fratelli Cuzio 42, Pavia, Italy

⁴ Uponor AB, Hackstavägen 1, Västerås, Sweden

ewa.zukowska@eurecat.org

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ABSTRACT

The life cycle assessment (LCA) is a methodology for assessing environmental impacts associated with the stages of the life cycle (LC) of a product, process, or service. This paper compares the results of the entire LCA (cradle-to-grave analysis) of a hybrid heating geothermal system that includes a novel hybrid heat pump 8kW and set of heating components integrated in a novel ground source heat pump (GSHP) concept which was installed in a building located on the Aran Islands (Ireland) within the framework of the H2020 GEOFIT project against the heating system, that existed before the retrofitting. The building selected for the demonstration had in its original version a 21kW diesel boiler (Firebird model S/90) used for heating and an emission system based on 9 conventional radiators with individual on / off control located in different rooms, as well as a coal stove in the living room.

To determine the building's annual thermal energy before and after retrofitting, energy simulations were performed using IDA Indoor Climate and Energy 4.8 software, taking into account equipment efficiency data and other key parameters measured on site and needed to run the simulation. Whereas the SimaPro v.9.1 software and Ecoinvent v.3.6 database were used to calculate the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

The results show that the innovative GSHP heating system (after GEOFIT) is a better alternative than the conventional one (before GEOFIT), mainly in terms of heat generation with lower energy demand, which is also reflected in the environmental aspect. The new heating system can reduce annual operational emissions of CO₂ by more than 89% in comparison to the reference one.

1. INTRODUCTION

Buildings generate about 39% of annual global CO₂ emissions, of those total emissions, building operations are responsible for 28%, while building materials and construction are responsible for 11% (UNEP, 2019). This data comes before COVID-19 which caused a 10% decrease, although the decrease appears to be temporary as emissions will pick up again as economic activity increases (UNEP, 2021). The European Union's Green Deal requires participants to reduce at least 40% GHG emissions compared to that of 1990 levels to achieve at least 32% share for renewable energy and to improve the energy efficiency at least by 32.5%. In this context, Ireland's National Energy and Climate Plan to 2020 (NECP) commits Ireland to an average annual reduction of GHG emissions by 7% annually in 2021-2030 (a reduction of 51% over a decade) and to achieve net zero emissions by 2050 (SEAI, 2021).

The main source of heating in Ireland was coal and peat, which dominated until the 1950s, in the 1960s crude oil and town gas gained popularity, and from the mid-1970s to the end of the 1980s, solid fuel returned, and crude oil and natural gas has found most of the consumers in the last 25 years. Since 2008, building codes in Ireland require new homes to be equipped with some form of renewable energy source (RES) (Ireland 2050).

One of the RES can be geothermal energy, that includes energy obtained from the inside of the Earth, whether in the form of electricity or heat. This source of energy looks to be an excellent alternative to reducing GHG emissions from heating and cooling buildings with fossil fuels, and thanks to its constant supply of concentrated energy, it can support the transition towards a low-carbon economy. In this context geothermal energy can play a crucial role in Ireland as well as whole European energy market.

This paper evaluates the GEOFIT's enhanced geothermal system with a novel heat pump for heating a building in a climate dominated by heat demand and underline the benefits which has bring its adoption from the point of view of environmental protection. This new technological solution is in line with the expectations of the energy market, which is predicted that heat pumps will meet 20% of buildings' thermal energy needs by 2030, compared to 5% in 2019 (IEA, 2021).

2. LCA METHODOLOGY

The LCA is a standardized methodology to assess the environmental impacts of a product, system through its LC. The ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006 standards provide the framework for performing an LCA, which consist of four phases.

The first phase is to define the goal and scope of the assessment, its objectives, functional unit (FU), and system boundaries. The scope of the study determines which processes should be included in the inventory phase of the assessment. In the second phase, the life cycle inventory (LCI) includes information on all the inputs and outputs associated with a product or service, i.e., material and energy requirements, as well as emissions and waste. The third phase is the impact assessment, where the potential contribution of each component to predefined environmental impact categories is calculated. Once the impact has been calculated, the fourth and final step of the assessment is the interpretation, where the results of the calculations are summarized and discussed.

The LCA analysis of this study was performed in accordance with the already mentioned European ISO standards and ILCD Handbook developed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. Furthermore, LCA has as well based in the "Life Cycle Phases of Energy Systems" reported in PCR UN CPC 171 and 173 *Electricity, steam and hot/cold water generation and distribution* and EN 15978. Software SimaPro v9.1 was used to calculate the emission of greenhouse gases (GHG).

2.1 Goal and Scope

The main goal and scope of this LCA study was to determine the environmental impact generated by the construction, operation, maintenance, and end of life (LCA) of a novel GSHP heating system which was developed within the framework of the GEOFIT project and to compare it with the energy sources used so far.

In this context, this study focuses on the system wide analysis of a hybrid geothermal system installed on the Aran Islands (Ireland), which presents a heating solution for a typical single-family house. Additionally, a comparative analysis was carried out with the heating system that was before the retrofitting (baseline scenario), which used only conventional heating methods, such as coal and diesel.

In terms of operational energy, the performance of the heating systems before and after retrofitting was

compared using indoor climate simulations via energy modelling software IDA-ICE 4.8 (Indoor Climate and Energy performance simulation program).

Functional unit

In order to compare both situations (before and after GEOFIT), two FU were selected to describe results and conclusions:

1. FU: defined as the annual heating energy demand to maintain a comfortable indoor building temperature of 20-21° C in the residential building on the Aran Islands (Ireland). Study period of 50-years (average building lifespan).
2. FU: defined as the generation of 1 kWh of thermal energy delivered to the residential building on the Aran Islands (Ireland) to maintain indoor comfort temperature of 20-21° C.

System boundaries

According to the PCR UN CPC 171 and 173 report, the system under investigation is divided into two modules: upstream and core. For this analysis above document, EN 15978 and the model proposed by Maria Laura Parisi et al. (2020) have been adapted for the Aran building purposes and the cradle-to-grave system boundaries including the following phases outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: LCA stages for Aran heating systems

Upstream Module (Secondary data)		Core Module (Primary data)					
Production		Construction & Installation		Operation & Maintenance		End of Life	
Raw materials	Energy	Thermal system components	Energy used for installation	Operational energy use /heating generation	Replacement of materials	Disposal	Recycling

The upstream module includes the production processes for raw materials and energy consumed by the core module, which is associated with a residential building on the Aran Islands. Secondary data were collected from the Ecoinvent 3.6 LCA database.

The core module is represented by the construction, installation, operation, maintenance, and end of life stages of a thermal energy conversion system. The sources of primary data came from suppliers and operators of processes, systems or/and they were measured and collected in situ of the core module. For the purpose of this study the operational energy was simulated with the IDA-ICE software.

IDA ICE is a building energy simulation software. It is a whole-year detailed and dynamic multi-zone simulation application for study of indoor climate as well as the energy performance of the entire building.

2.2 Life cycle Inventory

Case study

The single-family house under study (Figure 1) is located on the Aran Islands off the western coast of Ireland. The climate in the area is of Northern Oceanic temperate type. The building was originally constructed in 1922 on limestone soil, and its total area is 117 m².

Figure 1: Residential building on the Aran Islands (Ireland)

The main changes under the heat energy retrofitting of the studied building concerned the following challenges:

- Improvement of the thermal properties of the building's external walls through thermal insulation
- Improvement of heat emission through the installation of an underfloor heating system
- Installation of an 8kW heat pump
- Installation of a geothermal heat exchanger (one borehole)

Heating the Aran building is required for six to seven months. The average temperature to be maintained during the heating season is around 20-21°C. Given that the Aran Islands have a Northern Oceanic climate, there is no need for cooling in summer.

To evaluate the operational energy use in the building's heating system, it was modelled in IDA-ICE. The model is validated comparing the simulation results to measured data of heating energy use and indoor air temperature, using locally measured weather data as a boundary condition. The comparison between measured and simulated indoor temperatures is presented in Figure 2. The measured temperature varies more than the simulated one due to imperfect control of the heating system and inconsistencies in e.g. the occupancy and internal loads. However, the overall match between the simulated and measured

temperatures is good, with the coefficient of variation of the root mean square error CV(RMSE) being 7.1%. According to ASHRAE guideline 14-2002, an hourly simulation model can be considered valid if the CV(RMSE) < 30%.

Figure 2: Model validation comparing the measured and simulated indoor temperatures

Before GEOFIT, the building used a diesel boiler (21 kW) to produce heat for a conventional radiator system. After the geothermal retrofit, the building is served by a hybrid heating system, where a floor heating system supplied by geothermal energy covers the base heating load, while the boiler and radiators are conserved to help cover peak loads. Both systems are modelled using the IWEC2 30-year average weather data to compare the systems' energy use before and after retrofit. Most significant parameters of the modelled building and the heating systems are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters used for the simulated building model

Parameter	Value	Unit
Heated area	94	m ²
Walls U-value	0.9-1.3	W/m ² K
Windows U-value	2.9	W/m ² K
Ceiling U-value	1.4	W/m ² K
Floor U-value	3.5	W/m ² K
Infiltration	3	l/m ² s
Internal gains	13	W/m ²
Indoor temperature setpoint	20	°C
Radiator supply temperature	55-70	°C
Floor heating supply temperature	35	°C
Occupants	4	-

The annual heating results of the Aran building, simulated with the software IDA Indoor Climate and Energy 4.8 are presented in Table 3. The results before GEOFIT are based on measured coal and diesel consumptions, which were used to validate the simulation model. The model was then simulated using the same boundary conditions alongside the hybrid heating system to estimate the heating energy use after GEOFIT. The listed electricity use refers to the electricity used by the ground source heat pump, whereas the geothermal heat refers to heating energy produced by the heat pump. For simulation purposes, the design outdoor temperature for heating is 1.2°C according to the Irish Meteorological Service. (Met

Éireann, n.d.), and the underfloor heating installed as part of the retrofitting takes up 94 m² of surface.

Table 3: Annual heating energy results for Aran case building obtained via IDA-ICE simulation

	Before GEOFIT (kWh/Year)	After GEOFIT (kWh/Year)
<i>Electricity grid mix</i>	-	5 489.97
<i>Coal</i>	20 446.41	-
<i>Diesel</i>	17 776.83	0
Output heating geothermal (SCOP of 8 kW HP: 2.94)	-	16 140.50
Output heating coal stove (Efficiency: 80%)	16 357.13	-
Output heating 21 kW diesel boiler (Efficiency 46%)	8 177.34	0
TOTAL output heating	24 534.47	16 140.50

As can be seen in the table above, the annual results of heating energy generation for the Aran building after GEOFIT is reduced by approx. 34% (8394 kWh/year) thanks to the improvement of the building's energy efficiency by insulating the external walls.

Life cycle inventory (LCI) with the characteristics of two heating systems and their components considered in this study are summarised in the Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4: Main data and characteristics of the Aran Islands building before GEOFIT

<i>LC phases</i>	<i>Components</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Lifespan</i>	<i>Raw materials / Energy</i>	<i>Amount</i>	<i>Source</i>
Operation	Coal stove (<i>Efficiency 80%</i>)	1	Annually	Coal	20 446.41 kWh	IDA-ICE simulation
	Diesel boiler 21 kW (DHW) (<i>Efficiency 46%</i>)	1	Annually	Diesel	17 776.83 kWh	IDA-ICE simulation

Table 5: Main data and characteristics of the Aran Islands building after GEOFIT

<i>LC phases</i>	<i>Components</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Lifespan</i>	<i>Raw materials / Energy</i>	<i>Amount</i>	<i>Source</i>
Construction	Borehole heat exchanger 138 m depth, 130 mm of diameter	1	50 years	Mortar (Fischer GeoSolid® 240HS)	2700 kg	Provided by GEOFIT, Ecoinvent 3.6
				Water	1200 kg	
				Diesel	271 kg	
	Borehole pipes PE100 PN16 SDR11	1	50 years	HDPE	149 kg	Provided by GEOFIT, Ecoinvent 3.6
				Copper	36.09 kg	
	Heat pump 8 kW (210 kg)	1	20 years	Polyvinylchloride	1.64 kg	
				Elastomer, tube insulation	16.41 kg	
				Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled	32.81 kg	
				Stainless steel	123.05 kg	
				refrigerant R410A	1.72 kg	
				Lubricating oil (Polyolester oil)	2.79 kg	
				Electricity, mix grid	112 kWh	
	Buffer tank 200 l (65 kg)	1	50 years	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled	58.5 kg	
Copper				5.8 kg		
Floor Heating with PE-Xa 9.9 x 1.1 mm pipe	1	50 years	HDPE	35.7 kg	Provided by GEOFIT	
			EPS	56.2 kg		

				electronic component	5 kg		
	Floor installation	1	50 years	Mortar	1 684.8 kg	Provided by GEOFIT	
				Tiles (floor)	28 m ² (658 kg)		
				Wooden laminate	54 m ² (0.54 m ³)		
	External Thermal Insulation	1	30 years	EPS, Graphite	162 kg	Provided by GEOFIT	
				Rockwool	1771.2 kg		
Operation	Heat pump 8 kW (<i>SCOP 2.94</i>)	1	Annually	Electricity grid mix	5 489.97 kWh	IDA-ICE simulation	
	Diesel boiler (<i>Efficiency 46%</i>)	1	Annually	Diesel	0 kWh	IDA-ICE simulation	
Maintenance	Borehole heat	1	Annually	Borehole heat	0 unit / 50 years		
	Heat pump 8 kW	1	Annually	Heat pump 8 kW	2 units /50 years		
			Annually	Refrigerant R410A (from the initial 6%)	0.10 kg / year	(Greening & Azapagic, 2012)	
	Buffer tank 200 l	1	Annually	Buffer tank 200 l	0 unit / 50 years		
	Floor Heating	1	Annually	Floor Heating	0 unit / 50 years		
	External Thermal Insulation	1	Annually	External Thermal Insulation	1 unit / 50 years		
End of life	Heat pump 8 kW			Recycling 100%	-210 kg		
	Buffer tank 200 l	1		Recycling 100%	-65 kg		
	Borehole heat, Floor heating, External thermal insulation, Borehole heat	1			Recycling Plastics 85%	-1,862.4 kg	(EPA, 2021):
					Landfill Plastics 15%	328.7 kg	(EPA, 2021):
					Recycling mortar 23%	-394.5 kg	(EPA, 2021):
					Landfill mortar 77%	1,320.3 kg	(EPA, 2021):
			Electronics recycling 100%	- 5 kg			

Lifespan

The lifespan of thermal energy systems has a significant impact on environmental performance, mainly in the maintenance phase of the LCA, where replacement of materials at the end of their useful life is considered, Table 5.

The replacement in this study corresponds to the lifespan of the components including EoL. The number of replacements is linked to estimated service life of the materials according to the EN 15978, where the only full number of replacements is allowed

Impact assessment method

The environmental impact of LCA was considered the GHG emission, which was calculated using the SimaPro v9.1 software and the Ecoinvent v3 database.

The method which was selected for environmental impact calculation is the IPCC 2013 which was used to

evaluate 100-years global warming potential (GWP 100a) of different emissions. This method is based on data published by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, and expresses the emissions of GHG generated, in kilograms of CO₂ equivalent, over a time horizon of 100 years.

2.2 Results and discussion

The environmental impact related to the entire LCA (cradle-to-grave) of the two studied scenarios: building before GEOFIT (reference) and building after GEOFIT were assessed using the GWP 100a emission indicator. The details of this study are presented below.

GHG emissions

The results of the LCA analysis of the environmental impact of GHG emissions in terms of a 50-year study period are presented in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Analysis of GHG emissions at each stage of the LCA (over a period of 50 years) of the residential building on the Aran Islands retrofitted under the GEOFIT project

As illustrated in Figure 3, in terms of GHG emission, the post-GEOFIT building (green bars) performs better than the pre-retrofitting building (grey bars). The building after GEOFIT (green bars) emits about 88% (710 tonne CO₂ eq.) less GHG than building before retrofitting over 50 years study. The main contribution to the environment has the operation stage 91% in the whole LCA, which is responsible for more than 88% (718 ton CO₂ eq.) of the reduction of emission GHG to the atmosphere compared to the reference building. The other LCA stages have a minor role in GHG emissions.

The results of the GHG emissions of the construction stage, including comprehensive retrofitting of the building as part of the GEOFIT project, under which, in addition to installing the GSHP heating system, the external walls were insulated, are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: GHG emissions of each component installed in the Aran Islands building under GEOFIT project

The hotspots analysis of each installed component, shown in Figure 4, presents on GEOFIT system a visible dominance of the borehole heat exchanger about 32.3% (1228 kg CO₂ eq.), next one is the external thermal insulation of the building about 26.1% (990 kg CO₂ eq.) for the production of which insulating

materials, such as: EPS foam board and Rockwool were used. This last one is responsible for 79% of GHG emission. The third dominant component is a heat pump 8 kW, about 25.4% (962 kg CO₂ eq.) for the production of which mainly recyclable metals, such as: steel and copper are used. The rest of the components, such as: Floor Heating UPONOR about 13.1 % (495 kg CO₂ eq.) and buffer tank 200 l about 3.2% (120 kg CO₂ eq.) has a negligible impact on the emission of greenhouse gases to the atmosphere.

However, over the long-term analysis, GHG emissions in the construction LCA stage are significant only in the first year of the system implantation, the relatively long lifespan of the GSHP components (1 borehole heat exchanger, buffer tank 200l, heat pump 8kW), radiant heating floor and external thermal insulation will give a visible margin of reduction of CO₂ emissions because the energy generated by a novel GEOFIT system is cleaner and causes significantly lower by about 89% (16 203 kg CO₂ eq. per year) compared to a traditional diesel boiler and coal stove system. It means that the new system, after 30 years of operation, which is an average lifespan of the geothermal system (Parisi et al., 2020) is able to reduce by around 431 t GHG emission.

For detailed illustration, Figure 5 presents the dominance analysis of GHG emissions, expressed in kg CO₂ eq. from various energy sources for the generation of 1 kWh of thermal energy by the heating systems before and after GEOFIT.

Figure 5: Environmental hotspots analysis of 1 kWh thermal energy generated by reference and GEOFIT system

Figure above shows that 1 kWh of thermal energy generated and distributed to the Aran Islands building by the reference system is 0.660 kg CO₂ eq./kWh_{th} and is responsible for 64% of GHG emissions from coal (0.424 kg CO₂ eq./kWh_{th}) and 36% from diesel (0.236 kg CO₂ eq./kWh_{th}).

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On the other hand, the GHG emission from the GEOFIT geothermal heating system (100% from electricity grid mix of 8kW heat pump) is only 0.114 kgCO₂ / kWh_{th}, which is within the range indicated in the literature (Laura Cole; 2020).

Summing up, the GEOFIT system emits approximately 83% (0.546 kg CO₂ eq / kWh_{th}) less CO₂ into the atmosphere than the reference system.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The LCA study was conducted for a novel GSHP concept developed within the GEOFIT project and installed in a residential building on the Aran Islands (Ireland).

The LCA analysis shows that the GEOFIT heating system is able to reduce by over 89% annual CO₂ emissions to the atmosphere from the operation phase compared to the reference system. This proves that the new geothermal concept is more beneficial and environmentally friendly than the traditional heating approach using diesel and coal.

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